

Shaping a Sustainable Future with
Digital Product-Service Ecosystems

D8.2 – Data Management Plan DMP – Initial version

31 March 2025

Dissemination Level: Public Distribution

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

© 2025 Copyright in this document remains vested in the PSS-Pass Project Partners.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project Title	Methods and Tools Supporting Digital Product Service System Passport
Work package	WP 8
Task	T 8.1
Due date	31.03.2025
Deliverable lead	ATB
Authors	All partners
Version	1.0

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description of change
0.1	06.02.2025	Document initiated
0.2	07.03.-21.03.2025	Partners Contributions
1.0	31.03.2025	Final Version

PSS-PASS CONSORTIUM & CONTACT

Partner	Partner Name	Short Name	Country
	INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMTECHNIK BREMEN	ATB	DE
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI BERGAMO	UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI BERGAMO	UB	IT
<small>MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE</small>	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TEC	ES
	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION	UNP	PT
	ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA	ENG	IT
	THE OPEN GROUP	TOG	UK
CIRCULAR ECONOMY FOUNDATION	CIRCULAR ECONOMY FOUNDATION	CEF	BE
	F6S EU TECH INNOVATION NETWORK DESIGNATED ACTIVITY COMPANY	F6STECH	IE
	F6S NETWORK	F6S UK	UK
	ELECTROLUX ITALIA	ELX	IT
<small>AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT</small>	OAS AG	OAS	DE
	IMPORT ARRASATE	TER	ES

WWW.PSS-PASS.EU

Coordinator

ATB - Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen
 Wiener Str. 1
 28359 Bremen
 Germany
 Web: www.atb-bremen.de

Contact

Christian Wolff
 E-Mail: wolff@atb-bremen.de
 Phone: +49 421 22092 33

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the initial Data Management Plan of the PSS–Pass project and the initial data sets that have been identified to support the three pilot evaluations for industrial validation of the project technologies. The data sets are described in accordance with the European Commission guidelines for Research Data Management and include the key attributes of data type, format, metadata, use of standards and sharing modalities. Further data sets associated with benchmarks and other facilities to support the development of the PSS–Pass components may be utilised, and any additional data sets will be described in future Data Management Plan updates, as the technology development tasks progress and relevant data sets are developed or adopted.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION.....	7
	1.1 Purpose of this document.....	7
	1.2 Data Lifecycle.....	7
	1.3 Intended Audience	9
	1.4 Structure of the document	9
2	PROJECT DATA POLICIES.....	10
	2.1 Participation in the Research Data Management.....	10
	2.2 IPR Management and Security	10
	2.3 Personal Data Protection	10
	2.4 Ethics.....	11
3	FAIR DATA.....	12
	3.1 Findability.....	12
	3.2 Accessibility.....	13
	3.3 Interoperability.....	13
	3.4 Reusability	13
	3.5 Further considerations.....	13
4	INITIAL PSS-PASS DATA SETS	15
	4.1 Pilot 1 – Electrolux: Home Appliances	17
	4.2 Pilot 2 – OAS: Complex Equipment	18
	4.3 Pilot 3 – TERNUA: Textile.....	20
	4.4 Data Sets used by RTD partners during development of PSS-Pass solutions.....	21
	4.4.1 Ontologies	21
	4.4.2 Life Cycle Assessment.....	22
	4.4.3 DT-Based Simulation Framework.....	23
5	CONCLUSION	24

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Data Lifecycle Elements	8
--	----------

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1: Summary of initial PSS–Pass data sets	15
TABLE 2: ELX Data Set – Chimera.....	17
TABLE 3: ELX Data Set – Maintenance Log	17
TABLE 4: OAS Data Set – Configuration	18
TABLE 5: OAS Data Set – PCF Data on Raw Materials	18
TABLE 6: OAS Data Set – Batch Protocol/Log.....	19
TABLE 7: TER Data Set – Materials Data.....	20
TABLE 8: TER Data Set – Models Data	20
TABLE 9: RTD Data Set – DPSSP Ontology	21
TABLE 10: RTD Data Set – Ecoinvent.....	22
TABLE 11: RTD Data Set – GaBi	22
TABLE 12: RTD Data Set – EU Environmental Footprint.....	23
Table 13: RTD Data Set – Washing Machine Dataset.....	23

ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence	H2020	Horizon 2020
CC	Creative Commons	HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
D	Deliverable	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
DMP	Data Management Plan	No.	Number
DPSSP	Digital Product Service System Passport	OA	Open Access
DT	Digital Twin	PCF	Product Carbon Footprint
e.g.	exempli gratia	PSS	Product Service System
EC	European Commission	RDM	Research Data Management
EU	European Union	RIA	Research and Innovation Action
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable	RTD	Research and Technological Development

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

The PSS–Pass project participates in the Research Data Management (RDM) under the Horizon Europe Program, and in the interest of supporting the PSS–Pass ecosystem seeks – whenever feasible – to share open data by making data sets used and created within the project publicly available. This will apply to data sets used for the pilot evaluations later in the project, as well as to data used in the development or laboratory validation of the work carried out under the research and development tasks.

This deliverable outlines the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for PSS–Pass, in alignment with the HE guidelines for data management plan creation . It identifies the initial classes of datasets that the project foresees to utilise and create, primarily with respect to the pilot evaluations, providing an outline of the type of data, format, metadata, and sharing modalities for the data sets identified in the early stage of the project.

The purpose of this DMP is to provide a description of the main elements of the data management policies that will be used by the consortium with regards to all the data sets that will be generated or adopted by the project. The DMP is not a fixed document and is intended to evolve during the operation of the PSS–Pass project. This initial version of the DMP includes an overview of the data sets to be produced and/or used by the project, and the specific conditions that are attached to them. Updated version of the DMP will provide more details and describe the practical data management procedures that have been implemented by the PSS–Pass project.

1.2 Data Lifecycle

The data management planning for the PSS–Pass project is intended to evolve over the project operation to eventually cover the entire data lifecycles for the data created or adopted by the project. Figure 1 depicts the typical lifecycle for a given data set. Data lifecycle support is an important aspect related to creating a sustainable PSS–Pass ecosystem, as evolving data sets can help sustain the ecosystem and create opportunities for new applications and services that further exploit the PSS–Pass results. Supporting policies and procedures concerning PSS–Pass–related data sets will be further analysed and outlined in later deliverables, addressing the PSS–Pass ecosystem, exploitation strategies and associated business models.

Figure 1: Data Lifecycle Elements¹

Figure 1 depicts a typical data set lifecycle, while there can be many variations. For example, some pilot data providers may utilise or share raw data from Data Collection sources without any Data Analysis.

Key elements to be considered in managing data within the data lifecycle are the following:

- File formats.
- Organisation and naming conventions.
- Quality control.
- Access modalities.
- Persistence and recovery.
- Metadata and data conversion.
- Sharing and preservation.

These elements are addressed for the initial data sets described in this plan in accordance with the European Commission guidelines. At this stage of the PSS-Pass project, having defined the targeted pilot systems and associated industrial and technical requirements, some of the data set information provided should be considered preliminary and subject to change.

¹ Source: University of Virginia Library, Research Data Services

1.3 Intended Audience

This deliverable is intended for internal use within the PSS–Pass project, to establish a view of the initial data sets that have been identified for use in the project’s technology evaluations and development tasks, and to clarify the planning that is already taking place within the project concerning access and preservation of data. This report provides initial guidance on data management to the project partners and is particularly relevant for partners responsible for data collection and pilot evaluations. It should be considered a first snapshot, which will evolve throughout the project as further details concerning the technologies and industrial evaluations are specified and additional procedures and infrastructures are created or adapted for storing and managing project related data.

1.4 Structure of the document

This deliverable has been structured with three main sections, addressing the different aspects of data management within the PSS–Pass project as follows:

- Section 2 provides an overview of the initial data policies established for the project.
- Section 3 provides an overview of the FAIR data policies established for the project.
- Section 4 describes the data sets that have already been identified for use in the pilot evaluations and development tasks, some of which are already existing, while others will be created during the project operation.

A final section with conclusions is also provided.

2 Project Data Policies

2.1 Participation in the Research Data Management

The PSS–Pass project participates in the Research Data Management (RDM) launched by the European Commission in conjunction with the Horizon Europe Programme. The consortium strongly believes in the concepts of open research and development, and in the benefits that the European RTD and software development community can draw from allowing reuse of data on much larger scales across Europe. Therefore, whenever feasible, data produced by the project can potentially be published under open access procedures – though this objective may be constrained in view of other principles related to IPR and security, as described below, as well as partners’ exploitation interests.

2.2 IPR Management and Security

Many project partners have or will have Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) on the project technologies and data, which for some partners are essential for economic sustainability. The PSS–Pass project consortium will therefore have an obligation to protect these data and to publish data only if the concerned partner(s) have explicitly granted authorisation. Another effect of IPR management is that some of the data collected through the PSS–Pass project may be of high value for application and service providers, and therefore due consideration of the business models and ecosystem should be taken in advance of open access decisions for project data sets. All measures should therefore be taken to prevent data from being leaked or hacked, which could potentially undermine the ecosystem planning for the project or the commercial opportunities for PSS–Pass project partners. Repositories used by the project for data that have potential commercial value will be secured until decisions concerning open access are taken by the respective partner(s), and in view of the planned business models within the PSS–Pass ecosystem.

For sensitive data, a holistic security approach will be applied to protect the three main pillars of information security: confidentiality, integrity, and availability. The security approach will consist of an assessment of security risks for each data set, followed by an impact analysis. This analysis will be performed on the information and data processed by the PSS–Pass solutions, their flows and any risk associated to their processing. Particular attention will be placed on the assessment of any data sets containing personally identifiable information.

2.3 Personal Data Protection

For some of the activities to be carried out by the project, it may be necessary to collect basic personal data (e.g. name, e-mail address, activities, role) for use in the pilot evaluations, even

though the project will avoid collecting such data unless deemed necessary. Such data will be handled in compliance with the EU's Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC¹, and more recently the General Data Protection Regulation that came into effect in May 2018, aiming at protecting personal data. National legislations in Belgium, Finland, Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, and the United Kingdom applicable to the project will also be strictly followed. All personal data collection during the project will be done after giving the test subjects full details on the evaluation experiments to be conducted, and after providing options to opt out of collection of any personal data. Any existing data sets that contain personal data will be anonymised by the data set provider for use in the project, to prevent inadvertent access to personal data by project partners.

2.4 Ethics

The related ethics topics will be addressed in several deliverables. These will provide an overview of key legal, ethical, and risk management considerations for implementing AI systems as part of the PSS-Pass project. The reports aim to help the project navigate the complex landscape of AI ethics and proactively identify and mitigate potential risks and negative impacts. The following deliverables address these topics:

- D8.10 Ethics Requirements – Initial version
- D8.11 Ethics Requirements – Final version

3 FAIR data

A set of general provisions are being established that provide the rules to ensure that the datasets being developed within the project are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The provisions will be set in place throughout the project with the main objective of raising awareness among the project partners with a specific focus on the industrial partners to support them into their FAIR journey. The PSS–Pass project is going to use the work done in the OntoCommons project² where the OntoCommons solutions provided a way to harmonise data documentation through ontologies and taxonomies, making the data FAIR, and enabling intra- and cross-domain interoperability. This will be complemented with an overview of the FAIR Principles, and examples of concrete implementation of the FAIR principles in industry. Several online resources are available to help the PSS–Pass partners in their journey such as:

- <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/home.html>, an online, open and live resource with recipes that help users to make and keep data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/>, a three-point framework that formulates the essential steps towards the end goal, a global Internet of FAIR Data and Services where data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) for machines.

At the end of the PSS–Pass project, we will assess the FAIRness of the data sets listed in section 4 by following the FAIR guiding principles described by Wilkinson et. al.³ and adopted by many institutions⁴. This will be leveraged with the IPR issues faced by each of the data sets (in particular the industrial data sets). The principles are described in a nutshell in the following sub-section.

3.1 Findability

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

2 10.5281/zenodo.10891060

3 Wilkinson et al., the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data. 2016 Mar 15;3:160018. doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.

4 <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/introduction/brief-FAIR-principles.html>

- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data is registered or indexed in a searchable resource

3.2 Accessibility

- A1. (meta)data is retrievable by its identifier using a standardized communications protocol
- A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
- A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata is accessible, even when the data is no longer available

3.3 Interoperability

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

3.4 Reusability

- R1. meta(data) is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
- R1.1. (meta)data is released with a clear and accessible data usage license
- R1.2. (meta)data is associated with detailed provenance
- R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

3.5 Further considerations

Furthermore, the DMP addresses also the project research outputs, and carefully considers aspects related to the data security and ethical aspects. The latter is addressed in the PSS-Pass deliverable D8.10 (initial version) and D8.11 (final version) of Ethics Requirements.

For project research outputs under Horizon Europe, Open Access (OA) to scientific peer-reviewed publications remains the norm as the previous framework of H2020, but now has an explicit obligation to license the publication “*under the latest available version of the Creative*

Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights (see Annex 5 to the model grant agreement, additional obligations for article 17). An exception exists for monographs and other long-text formats, where *“the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND)”*⁵. the PSS-Pass partners will follow these guidelines with all scientific publications within the project.

⁵ https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/open-access-obligations-horizon-europe-what-are-cc-licences-2021-11-15_en

4 Initial PSS–Pass Data Sets

The different data sets that – according to the initial plans in an early stage of the project – will be gathered and processed by the PSS–Pass project are described in the following subsections. The descriptions follow the guidelines provided by the European Commission with respect to data set characteristics. These initial data sets will be updated and extended with additional data sets by the project partners responsible for the different pilot evaluations to be conducted later in the project, as well as by partners involved in the development of the core technology components where benchmark and other relevant data sets may be generated or adopted during development. Table 1 provides a summary of the initial datasets that have been identified in relation to the evaluations to be carried out for the three project pilot cases as well as the development testing of the PSS–Pass solutions.

TABLE 1: Summary of initial PSS–Pass data sets

No.	Pilot / RTD Topic	Data Sets
1	Pilot 1 – Electrolux: Home Appliances	DS_ELX_001 Chimera
2	Pilot 1 – Electrolux: Home Appliances	DS_ELX_002 Maintenance log
3	Pilot 2 – OAS: Complex Equipment	DS_OAS_001 Manuals, Specifications, Maintenance Plans
4	Pilot 2 – OAS: Complex Equipment	DS_OAS_002 PCF by OAS Customers Raw Material Suppliers
5	Pilot 2 – OAS: Complex Equipment	DS_OAS_003 Batch Protocol/Log
6	Pilot 3 – TERNUA: Textile	DS_TER_001 Materials data
7	Pilot 3 – TERNUA: Textile	DS_TER_002 Models data
8	RTD – Ontologies	DS_RTD_001 DPSSP set of ontologies
9	RTD – Life Cycle Assessment	DS_RTD_002 Ecoinvent
10	RTD – Life Cycle Assessment	DS_RTD_003 GaBi
11	RTD – Life Cycle Assessment	DS_RTD_004 EPLCA
12	RTD – DT-Based Simulation Framework	DS_RTD_005 Washing-machine dataset

The description of each data set follows the European Commission provided template and includes the following elements:

- Data Set Name – used to keep track of different data sets.
- Contributor(s) – organisations that are responsible for generating/providing the data. This can be a project partner, but also external organisations can be contributors.
- Description – briefly summarises the type of data elements that exist, or will be created, and their format.
- Standards – any standards that the data set might follow in the way elements are described or structured.
- Quality Assurance – procedures that might be in place to ensure quality is maintained such as consistency or reliability of the data.
- Access – indication if the existing data set or data to be created in the PSS-Pass project will be publicly accessible or restricted.
- Archiving and preservation – indicates if facilities for preserving the data are provided by the responsible project partner, a third-party, or if the PSS-Pass project will need to create facilities (e.g. project website).

The above characteristics of each of the identified data sets are summarised in the following sections, which have been identified with respect to the pilot evaluation tasks to be carried out in the project as well as the main RTD tasks.

4.1 Pilot 1 – Electrolux: Home Appliances

TABLE 2: ELX Data Set – Chimera

Data set name or reference	DS_ELX_001 Chimera	
Contributor(s)	Electrolux	
Data set description and format	SQL Database, HW, SW configuration and version Type: excel file	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

TABLE 3: ELX Data Set – Maintenance Log

Data set name or reference	DS_ELX_002 Maintenance log	
Contributor(s)	Electrolux, eventually data simulated by partners	
Data set description and format	Maintenance intervention data	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

4.2 Pilot 2 – OAS: Complex Equipment

TABLE 4: OAS Data Set – Configuration

Data set name or reference	DS_OAS_001 Manuals, Specifications, Maintenance Plans	
Contributor(s)	OAS AG, OAS-Equipment Suppliers	
Data set description and format	Raw data sets as input for DPSSP: Manuals, Specifications, Maintenance Plans Type: PDF	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	Maintained by OAS AG	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

TABLE 5: OAS Data Set – PCF Data on Raw Materials

Data set name or reference	DS_OAS_002 PCF by OAS Customers Raw Material Suppliers	
Contributor(s)	OAS Customers Raw Material Suppliers	
Data set description and format	Product Carbon Footprint (PCF) of raw material directly from OAS Customers Raw Material Suppliers	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

TABLE 6: OAS Data Set – Batch Protocol/Log

Data set name or reference	DS_OAS_003 Batch Protocol/Log	
Contributor(s)	OAS Customers Factories	
Data set description and format	Batch Protocol/Log including data/information on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Consumption through to the entire process of production processes • Identified problems • Used equipment along with unique equipment reference number (pronto) • Operational hours and number of switches from pronto database based on equipment counters • Human operators involved in the service and their data/input • Status of the components • Data on energy mix (coal, wind, solar, etc.) which is powering the factory needed for PCF calculation 	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner <input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

4.3 Pilot 3 – TERNUA: Textile

TABLE 7: TER Data Set – Materials Data

Data set name or reference	DS_TER_001 Materials data	
Contributor(s)	TERNUA	
Data set description and format	Excel file containing information on materials: composition, size, tests made, treatments, certificates, sustainability etc	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

TABLE 8: TER Data Set – Models Data

Data set name or reference	DS_TER_002 Models data	
Contributor(s)	TERNUA	
Data set description and format	Excel file containing data on models (finished products): weight, size, certificates, origin country, ID etc. This data is connected to the corresponding information on the materials dataset.	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot Partner	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

4.4 Data Sets used by RTD partners during development of PSS–Pass solutions

4.4.1 Ontologies

TABLE 9: RTD Data Set – DPSSP Ontology

Data set name or reference	DS_RTD_001 DPSSP set of ontologies	
Contributor(s)	ATB, UB, TEC	
Data description set and format	DPSSP set of ontologies based on PSS ontology and set of industrial ontologies from IOF and OntoCommons. Format: RDF	
Standards (if any)	The ontology(ies) will be modelled in OWL format.	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public access	<input type="checkbox"/> Restricted access
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	
Archiving preservation and responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Project Partner	<input type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

4.4.2 Life Cycle Assessment

TABLE 10: RTD Data Set – Ecoinvent

Data set name or reference	DS_RTD_002 Ecoinvent	
Contributor(s)	Ecoinvent Association (http://www.ecoinvent.org/)	
Data description set and format	It contains more than 20,000 LCI datasets covering products/processes from a wide range of sectors. Format: xlsx, csv	
Standards (if any)	ILCD compliant	
Quality assurance (if any)	Data Quality Guidelines	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Pay service.	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Project Partner	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

TABLE 11: RTD Data Set – GaBi

Data set name or reference	DS_RTD_003 GaBi	
Contributor(s)	Sphera Solutions GmbH (https://www.gabi-software.com/)	
Data description set and format	It contains more than 15,000 LCI datasets covering products/processes from a wide range of sectors.	
Standards (if any)	ILCD compliant	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Pay service. Some information is not accessible at all	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Project Partner	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External Party
	<input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):

TABLE 12: RTD Data Set – EU Environmental Footprint

Data set name or reference	DS_RTD_004 EPLCA	
Contributor(s)	European Commission (https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EnvironmentalFootprint.html)	
Data description set and format	European Platform on LCA (EPLCA) ⁶ LCI datasets covering products/processes across a wide range of sectors. Format: Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) data format ⁷	
Standards (if any)	ILCD- and PEF-compliant	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input type="checkbox"/> Public Access <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other: Allowed only for PEF-compliant studies.	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Project Partner <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External Party <input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	

4.4.3 DT-Based Simulation Framework

Table 13: RTD Data Set – Washing Machine Dataset

Data set name or reference	DS_RTD_005 Washing-machine dataset	
Contributor(s)	Open Data (Siemens AG)	
Data description set and format	This folder contains multi-variate time series measurements, which are compatible with and can be used in AI Designer. All measurements contain a dataset showing energy consumption and motion data of a washing machine during different washing programs. Each measurement is stored both as raw and pre-processed data in different file formats. .parquet and .csv https://github.com/siemens/simatic-ai-launcher/blob/master/datasets/washing-machine/README.md	
Standards (if any)	---	
Quality assurance (if any)	---	
Access	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public Access <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted Access <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate)	
Archiving and preservation responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/> Project Partner <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External Party <input type="checkbox"/> PSS-Pass Project <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	

5 Conclusion

This plan provides an overview of the data sets that the PSS–Pass project will produce or adopt, together with related challenges and constraints that need to be taken into consideration. The analysis contained in this report supports the procedures and infrastructures to be implemented by the PSS–Pass project to efficiently manage the existing data that will be used, as well as data that will be produced within the project.

It is too early in the project to have a complete identification of the data sets that will be used or created by the project, as the user requirements have only recently been collected and substantial work on the design of the PSS–Pass technologies and identification of required data sets is still underway. Some of the data that will need to be collected is not yet sufficiently clear to be detailed with the required level of specificity to be included in this preliminary plan, and others will be identified later in the project. This first version of the plan should therefore be considered an initial view that will be updated periodically as the project tasks progress.

By project completion time, several PSS–Pass project partners will be owners or producers of relevant data, in particular those associated with the pilot evaluations. This implies specific responsibilities, and this initial version of the plan is intended to create awareness among the project partners regarding the importance of appropriate procedures with respect to collection, publication (in the case of open access data sets), and use of metadata to increase the value of data, as well as persistence of all the information necessary for the optimal use and reuse of PSS–Pass-related data sets to support the PSS–Pass ecosystem. Also, the importance of working in the direction of making all data sets FAIR will be a focus point among all PSS–Pass project partners.

Specific attention will be given to ensuring that the data sets made public neither break partners' IPR rules, nor regulations and good practices related to personal data protection. For this latter point, procedures such as systematic anonymisation of personal data have been anticipated whenever data created within the PSS–Pass project has potential for misuse or disclosure of personally identifiable information.

⁶ See <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

⁷ See <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/LCDN/developer/LCDDDataFormat.html>